

Determination of Some Physicochemical Properties of Soil from Vicinity of Chemistry Department, Bago University

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Abstract

In the research work, some physicochemical properties of soil from vicinity of chemistry department, Bago University have been determined. Some physicochemical parameters (texture, moisture, pH), organic matter, nutrients and relative abundance of elements of soil sample from study area have done by conventional and modern spectroscopic techniques. The texture class is sandy loam. The soil has found to have moisture contents 0.71% and pH 5.77, the contents of nutrients (nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium) were found to be 0.16%, 10.23 ppm and 4.88 mg/100g respectively. Low organic carbon content 1.67% and humus 2.88% were also observed. Relative abundance of elements in soil sample, Si 77.65%, Fe 11.50%, Ti 4.14%, K 3.74% and Ca 1.24% were also observed.

Keywords : Soil, vicinity of chemistry department, physicochemical properties

Introduction

Soil is defined as the upper layer of the earth. Soil is among our most important natural resources because of its own position in the landscape and its dynamic, physical, chemical and biological function. There are different types of soil and each type exhibits certain properties. The depending on the size of the particles in the soil, it can be classified into sandy soil, salty soil, clay soil, loamy soil, peaty soil and chalky soil. The moisture which is contained in the soil is a very important part of the soil as far as plant growth is concerned. Water is formed in the soil in various forms. They are hygroscopic moisture and capillary moisture, gravitational on water. pH is a measure of hydrogen ion concentration; a measure of the acidity or alkalinity of a solution. A pH less than seven is acidic, while it greater than seven is basic or alkaline. Organic matter has been found in the soil at the site of very important role to maintain and improve soil properties. Soil organic matter includes humus like substance in soil. Micronutrients are those elements which occur in substantial levels in plants materials or fluids in the plant. It includes carbon, hydrogen, oxygen, nitrogen, phosphorus, sulphur, potassium, calcium, and magnesium. Micronutrients are elements which are essential only at very low levels and generally are required for the function of essential enzymes. The essential micronutrients have been boron, chlorine, sodium, copper, iron, manganese, zinc, vanadium and molybdenum. ED-XRF spectroscopy is used for the quantitative determination of multi-elements in a wide range of sample types. The advantages of ED-XRF are rapid, non-destructive and multi-elements determinations from ppm to high weight percent of elements.

Materials and Method

Sample Collection and Sample Handling

Soil sample was collected from the vicinity of chemistry department, Bago University Campus. The sampling location were 17°16'05.2"N 96°28'20.9"E. The sample was taken about 20cm depth from the surface in zigzag manner.

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<u>Parameter</u>	<u>Method Used</u>
Texture	Pipette method
Moisture	Oven dry method
pH	pH meter
Nitrogen	Kjeldahl's method
Phosphorus	Truog's method
Potassium	Flame photometer
Relative abundant of element	ED-XRF

Results and Discussion

The texture class of soil sample from the vicinity of Chemistry Department, Bago University Campus was shown in Table 1. The type of texture class shown was sandy loam. From this texture class, the soil sample of present work shows both sandy and loamy-soil characters. Sandy soil retains a certain amount of moisture and nutrients. Loamy soil consists of sand. Silt and clay to some extent and it considered to be perfect soil for gardening.

The moisture content of soil sample was shown in Table 2. The moisture content was found to be 0.71% and this is due to less water holding capacity of sandy soil.

The pH of soil sample from present research was shown in Table 2. The soil pH was found to be 5.77 that is acidic. Acidic soil pH in the range 4 to 6.5 and soil with pH value outside this range is usually toxic to most plants. Therefore the study soil with pH value 5.77 is suitable to grow most plants.

Table 1. Texture of Soil Sample from vicinity of Chemistry Department, Bago University Campus

Sr No	Soil type	Composition (%)	Texture Class
1	Sand	54.95	Sandy loam
2	Silt	43.00	
3	Clay	1.00	

Table 2. Chemical Parameters of Soil Sample from vicinity of Chemistry Department, Bago University Campus

Sr No	Parameters	Values
1	Moisture (%)	0.71
2	pH	5.77

The content of nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium in soil sample were shown in Table 3. The content of total nitrogen in soil sample was found to be 0.16%. A very low total nitrogen supply gives leaves with small cells and thick wall. The content of available phosphorus in soil sample was found to be 10.32ppm and that of potassium in soil sample was 4.88mg/100gm. From these determinations, relative lower content of essential nutrients (N, P, K) indicate that the study area is not suitable for cultivation.

Table 3 Distribution of Organic Carbon, Humus and NPK Contents in Soil Sample from vicinity of Chemistry Department, Bago University Campus

Sr No	Parameters	Values
1	Organic Carbon (%)	1.67
2	Humus (%)	2.88
3	Total Nitrogen (%)	0.16
4	Available phosphorus (%)	10.23
5	Available potassium (%)	4.88

From this result, the highest value of silicon 77.657% was found and the other element Fe, Tl, K and Ca were also found as the elemental constituents in soil sample. The relative abundance of elements in soil sample from vicinity of chemistry department, Bago University were studied by ED-XRF is shown in Table 4.

Table 4 Relative Abundance of Elements in Soil Sample from Vicinity of Chemistry Department, Bago University Campus

Sr No	Element	Content (%)
1	Si	77.657
2	Fe	11.504
3	Tl	4.140
4	K	3.740
5	Ca	1.242

Conclusion

From the determination of some physicochemical parameters of soil from vicinity of chemistry department, Bago University Campus, the following inferences have been deduced. From physical parameter determination, the type of textural class of soil sample was sandy loam. The chemical parameter such as moisture 0.71% was found in this soil sample. The moderately acidic soil pH 5.77 was observed in the study soil sample. From the determination of nutrient contents in soil sample, low content of nitrogen 0.16%, phosphorus 10.23 ppm and potassium 4.88 mg/100g were observed. Relative abundance of elements (Si, Fe, Tl, K and Ca) was found to be 77.657, 11.504, 4.140, 3.740, and 1.242 respectively. From the present investigation, the soil from study area has sandy loam which can be for cultivation. But, low content of essential nutrients (N, P, and K) indicated weakness of soil and to be modified soil to cultivate.

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References

- Baruah, T.C and Barthakur, H.P. (1999). "*A Textbook of Soil Analysis*". New Delhi: Vikas Publishing House Pvt. Ltd., 35-36.
- Russell, E.W. (1987). "*Soil conditions and Plant Growth*". London: Green and Co., Ltd., 320-403.
- Satake, M. and Mido, Y. (2003). "*Environmental Toxicology*". New Delhi: Toxic Effect of Metals", 2nd Edn, discovery Publishing House, 109-147.
- Tyagi, O.D and Mehra, M. (2000). "*A Textbook of Environmental Chemistry*". New Delhi: Amol Publication Pvt. Ltd., 102-106.
- Yin Yin May. (2007). "*Studies on tjr characteristics of Soil from Sites of Dagon University campus*". Yangon: MRes Thesis, Department of Chemistry, Dagon University.